

WAYS TO FORM COMPETENCIES IN TECHNOLOGY FOR ELEMENTARY STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article describes the methodology for organizing technology lessons in elementary grades and effective ways of developing students' competencies related to the science of technology. The article can be used by primary school teachers, students, undergraduates and parents.

Keywords: competence, profession, folk craft, communicative competence, competence of self-development, competence of socially active citizenship, competence of information processing, national and general cultural competence

The primary school technology classes provide for the development of technical creativity, ability, thinking of students, vocational guidance through teaching methods of technology-based processing of various and natural and metal and metal and non-metal materials in the course of the lesson, the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies on vocational guidance in the performance of Folk Crafts, Science, Electrical Engineering,

Attention has long been paid to the personal social qualities of teachers and, depending on the demand of each time, the requirements for an educator have improved and become more complex.

The Zoroastrian doctrine states that "the duty of the teacher — priests is to teach children knowledge in the way of good, to educate them in such a way as to separate the good from the bad, and to guide them in the right way". In his "yachts", a leader of teachers-teachers is praised, WHO, with a mental savagery, carries out the fight against evil, instills in the psyche of children a truthful word, pure reason, honest intention.

Also, the "Yasht" of "Avesto" "severely condemn the minds of children, their independent thinking," rusting "the minds of young people, weakening their attitudes towards life, hard work, weakening faith and impoverishing their faith.

It is the teacher's responsible duty to give students knowledge, as Ibn Sina expressed the following views on what a teacher's personality should be:

- *pressured in dealing with children, to be serious;*
- *to pay attention to how students absorb the knowledge that is given;*
- *use of various methods and forms in education;*
- *knowledge of the student's memory, ability to acquire knowledge, personal characteristics;*
- *getting interested in science;*
- *distinguishing and teaching the most important of the given knowledge;*
- *to give knowledge in accordance with the age, mental level of students;*
- *stressed the need to achieve that each word is at the level of arousal of children's emotions.*

The formation of competencies related to primary school technology science is defined in the national program and textbook, educational manuals. According to this, in the process of teaching the block-module of practical educational subjects, base competencies are formed in students.

Competence-we can understand field-specific knowledge, skills, qualifications, set of views, value and qualities of an individual, the ability to manifest or influence. Competence (lot.competo-I am achieving, I am worthy, I deserve) - means knowledge, experience in one area or another.

Science-specific competencies:

1. Knowledge of the types of items and products, methods of their preparation and processing, technological design and implementation competence:

2. Operational competence in the performance of psychomotor, functional and practical types of activities:

3. Choosing the right and conscious profession, competency to enter into social relationships
In particular, in the formation of communicative competencies, it is necessary to correctly pronounce, interpret and teach terms related to the Applied Sciences in mastering the state language, foreign languages, in the mutual performance of independent, creative thinking, practical training, in the formation of skills for performing creative project work, in the formation of skills for the written and oral fluency.

- being able to apply terms related to technology in the process of communication;
- simple statement of the appearance of the item to be prepared;
- ask questions on the topic as well as answer questions;
- compliance with the etiquette of treatment in communication, being able to listen to the opinion of the interlocutor, to explain his opinion.
- self-control in various situations at school, on the street, at home compliance with the culture of treatment when entering into communication;
- independent thinking based on the knowledge gained;
react independently to made items;
- being able to represent terms related to technology from foreign languages,
- to be able to enter into communication with his friends in the language of technology;
- to be able to logically put and answer questions based on the topic;
- to follow the culture of treatment in interaction, to be able to work in collective cooperation.
- defend and convince his position by analyzing the opinion of the interlocutor in the process of conversation on the science of technology;
- managing their passions in various conflict situations, knowing attitudes and making the necessary decisions, with a fair, truthful and positive approach to disagreements.

In the teaching of subjects, it is necessary to regularly use modern information and telecommunications tools that expand the possibilities of effective development of competence in working with information. In this case, it is recommended to use mobile devices (phones, tablets and other gadgets) in the formation of skills for students to search for information related to science from various sources, analyze it and work with the media in compliance with information security.

- television on technology science, viewing broadcast given on radio;
- perform studied work methods, study the information given in magazines and newspapers;

- to be able to perform didactic tasks, use information sources (TV, radio, audio-video recording, telephone), using media tools in finding terms related to technology science;
- compliance with media culture when opening files.
- be able to use existing information sources (Internet, TV, radio (audio-video recording), telephone, computer, email;
- tracking, sorting, processing, transmitting, maintaining security in storage and compliance with media culture in use of Media tools, necessary information related to the study of Technology Science;
- be able to work with documents found in everyday activities, search, study, analyze, apply resources related to technological maps and schemes;

In the formation of self-development competence, it is necessary to have universal qualities, love the motherland, acquire legal, economic knowledge, strive for innovations and, based on acquired theoretical knowledge, make independent decisions, be aware of the progressive and innovative changes taking place in society and teach them to be able to use them in everyday life.

- study of technology;
- adherence to cleanliness in the performance of practical work, listening to what adults say;
- To have such qualities as reading and studying subjects, hard work, correctness, respect in the circle of "skillful hands";
- to be the right word, to make the mistake of comrades, to adults;
- help the little ones, comrades, increase their knowledge through reading and learning;
- regular reading and study of books in different directions related to technology;
- correct understanding of self-error and flaw, trying to correct mistakes, self-control.
- deeper study of technology in directions;
- to bring directions to their inventions at the request of today, to get a companion in the profession of designer-fashion designer in the aircraft of each item;
- constant self-development as a person;
- to take responsibility for working in groups, to be able to become a leader, to be able to make the right decisions in various problem situations;
- to be able to properly exercise constitutional rights and duties;
- striving for physical, spiritual, spiritual and intellectual perfection.
- being able to show their abilities, depending on their interests as a person;
- to have human qualities, such as the choice of a conscious profession, honesty, correctness.

In the formation of socially active civil competence, civic duty consists in acquiring knowledge about social and political development, emergencies, environmental problems, understanding artistic and artistic works and the development of organizational qualities in their preservation.

- to know his student duty and duties, to follow him, to have his place in the classroom and in the family;
- helping adults, comrades and little ones of their own;
- participation and treatment in school and extracurricular activities to follow the culture;
- to have qualities such as respect for an adult, respect for a little one, to be able to understand his place and duties in the family; to know the duty of children and students to preserve the school building, classroom equipment, furniture, to follow it;
- knowing what rights he has in relation to his age, preserving classroom equipment, educational equipment;
- in the processes taking place at school, family, residence (various activities, Saturday, etc.) participation;
- not to be indifferent to what is happening in society, to express their attitude;
- understanding and conscious choice of the essence of professions;
- knowledge and observance of the rights, freedoms and duties of Man and citizens.

National and Universal competence:

- to dress orasta and always follow it, to be kind to friends, loved ones and those around you, to dress orasta, to take an example from an adult in walking, to appreciate his home, school, residential neighborhood;
- compliance with cleanliness, knowledge of national holidays, understanding of the rules of etiquette of the reader, knowledge of historical monuments in the land where he lives;
- know the types of art and be able to distinguish them from each other, analyze the works of art, follow the internal procedures of the school;
- to be able to distinguish between good and bad habits, to follow the etiquette of visiting, to know national values (national-cultural traditions, holidays, sayils) ;
- to study their historical, spiritual and cultural heritage in the directions of folk crafts, to preserve avilab, to honor traditions and rituals.
- to study their historical, spiritual and cultural heritage in the directions of folk crafts, to preserve avilab, to honor traditions and rituals;
- know the values of universal importance and treat it with respect.

Competence in mathematical literacy, awareness of Science and technology innovations and use:

- knowing how many people are in his family, who is older, who is younger, knowing the time it takes to come to school;
- be able to make daily plans; be able to draw different drawings in daily activities, know the days of holidays in our country;
- understanding the meaning of waste and savings and following it in everyday life;
- learning tools that will be needed in the course of the lesson, the use of raw materials in compliance with savings, knowing how to calculate the cost of one day;
- types of techniques and knowing when they appeared.
- to be aware of and be able to use the innovations of Science and technology that alleviate human labor, increase labor productivity and lead to favorable conditions.
- to be able to tell about the place of our country in the world community and the period of historical formation, to know the growth rates in all areas of our country during the years of independence;
- be able to read and use different formulas, models, drawings in everyday activities.

- when maintaining regulatory documents, it is recommended that the competencies regarding the base and science be written as follows.

Aesthetic culture and creativity competence.

- ❖ *perceives beauty and art;*
- ❖ *creative approach to independent work and creative thinking;*
- ❖ *works creatively, both solo and in collaboration with the team;*
- ❖ *having properly planned his creative activity, he will be able to critically assess the achieved result and enjoy his hard work;*
- ❖ *takes an alternative approach to problem solving and is able to make the right decisions;*
- ❖ *occupies the qualities of hard work, responsibility and workmanship, activity;*
- ❖ *can think constructively, put his ideas into practice;*
- ❖ *acquires design and research skills.*

Today, huge changes in parts of the national model, which consists of the educational system, the individual, the state and Society, Science and production, in particular, the radical transformation of the state and society, information and communication tools that have entered our lives, modern production technologies based on the latest achievements of Science and the emergence of different thinking young people, radically different.

